

A 3D porous electrode for real-time monitoring of microalgal growth and exopolysaccharides yields using Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Francisco C. Cotta^a, Raquel Amaral^a, Felipe L. Bacellar^a, Diogo Correia^a, Kamal Asadi^b, Paulo R.F. Rocha^{a,*}

^a Centre for Functional Ecology-Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, 3000-456, Portugal

^b Department of Physics, University of Bath, Claverton Down, Bath, BA2 7AY, UK

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ABSTRACT

Efficient monitoring of microalgal growth is vital for biomass industrialization and management of water resources. The precise determination of growth phases of biotechnologically relevant species of microalgae is necessary as it allows controlling the onset of target metabolites production such as exopolysaccharides (EPS). However, a low-cost, real-time and ultrasensitive measurement method for direct determination of real-time microalgal growth and EPS production does not exist. Here, we show that Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) in combination with porous polyurethane(PU)/poly (3,4- ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) electrodes can be used as a real-time probe to monitor microalgal growth and EPS production. We employ *Lobochlamys segnis* as a microalgae model system and show that growth can be continuously monitored with EIS for 14 days. A logistic growth rate from impedance data of $k_z = 0.75/\text{day}$ is found similar to that of conventional cell counting, of $k_{\text{cells}} = 0.85/\text{day}$, and is extracted from initial cell seeding densities as low as 10^5 cells/mL. Furthermore, the Ohmic resistance of electrolyte solution enables the detection of the time-point of maximum EPS production. The combination of ultra-large porous electrodes with EIS provides a platform for sensing and modelling of microalgae growth in real-time and opens new avenues for predictive water resource management as well as more effective large-scale microalgal production in biotechnological applications.

1. Introduction

Since their emergence on earth billions of years ago, microalgae have colonized almost all ecosystems in aqueous environments, air, and land, including very inhospitable ones at the edge of life's possibilities (Pierre et al., 2019). The reasons why they thrive are related to metabolic coping, keeping their fragile unicellular condition safe from deleterious environmental effects. Protective metabolites have bioactive properties and are attractive to biotechnological industries investing in microalgal biomass or biorefineries for obtaining lipids (feedstock or biofuels), proteins, fatty acids, carotenoids (food/feed, bioplastics, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals) and carbohydrates (food enhancers, bioethanol, cosmetics, medical applications) (Calijuri et al., 2022), (Benedetti et al., 2018), (Xiao and Zheng, 2016). The major secretion released by microalgae are exopolysaccharides (EPS), which protects the cells and also serves as energy sources for symbiotic heterotrophs. Microalgal EPS

production rate and monosaccharide composition varies according to the species, environmental conditions (Pierre et al., 2019) and growth phase (Xiao and Zheng, 2016). An important model species for EPS production has been the *Lobochlamys segnis* (Scranton et al., 2015), (Masi et al., 2023) where up to 25% of the total organic production are polysaccharides (Khan et al., 2018), (Proschold et al., 2001), (Schiano di Visconte et al., 2021).

Accurate EPS production depends on the actual microalgal growth rate. Hence, monitoring through periodic culture sampling is performed, where typically initial cell seeding densities are higher than 10^6 cells/ml (Bohutskyi et al., 2016). Yet, current culture sampling methods, or biomass sampling often requires multiple and ineffective steps in a laboratory, including sedimentation, flocculation and/or centrifugation performed by qualified personnel (Havlik et al., 2015). Recent monitoring advances involve aggregation-induced emission active nanoprobes to optically visualize EPS distribution (Yan et al., 2021), (Lin et al.,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: procha@uc.pt (P.R.F. Rocha).

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2021), (Kim et al., 2022) and commercially available fluorescent probes which measures microalgae-only in a quasi-continuous away – even though the fluorescence intensity does not currently provide effective detection resolutions and is strongly affected by the surrounding pH.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is emerging as an analytical *in-situ* tool which provides quantitative information on cellular adhesion and growth rates (Caeiro et al., 2025), particularly in nanometer-scale bacterial cells in suspension or immobilized on a functionalized electrode-surface (Yang et al., 2004). Biofilm formation across the electrode surface, comprising clusters of bacteria embedded in a self-produced matrix originates time-dependent alterations of the real and imaginary impedance components (Yang et al., 2004), (Yang and Li, 2006), (Yang et al., 2003). EIS typically employs sub-micrometer sized electrodes for investigating bulk and interfacial electrical changes on an electrode surface (Zhang et al., 2018), (Elghajji et al., 2021). However, microalgae are not sub-micrometer sized and typically measures longer than 20 μm in length.

In addition, contrary to bacteria which often have a doubling time of 20 min (Jin et al., 2012), microalgae can have a much slower doubling time, of up to 3 days (Silva et al., 2024). To detect microalgae growth rates and EPS yields the electrode surface area must be larger than conventional areas to accommodate larger microalgae cells and electrochemically stable to accurately record growth kinetics for at least several weeks.

Here we develop a real-time growth monitoring technology for microalgae based on 3D porous electrodes and EIS. We drastically increase the areal cell density of conventional and often used planar metallic electrodes by using 3D porous electrodes based on polyurethane sponges (PU) dip-coated with conducting polymer poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS). The growth dynamics and EPS production of distinct seeding densities of the model species *Lobochlamys segnis* are measured and benchmarked against standard growth methods during a full growth curve of 14 days.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fabrication of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes

Commercially available polyurethane (PU) foams (Eurospuma, 3049 PR) were cut using a Gunville Foam Cutter, into a cylinder shape having 5.5 mm diameter and 1 cm height. PU cylinders were degreased with detergent and distilled water, followed by cleaning with acetone and a 10-min ultrasonic bath in distilled water, then dried with compressed air (Fig. 1A–i). PU cylinders were further cleaned and hydrophilized with oxygen plasma (Diener Atto, 40 kHz 200 W) for 20 min (Fig. 1A–ii). PU cylinders were on a stainless-steel grid tray specially designed to favour plasma access to the external and internal surface during the oxygen plasma treatment. The bulk of the foam was hydrophilized, as shown in Fig. S1. The coating solution was prepared by mixing 19 mL of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) (Heraeus Clevis PH 1000, 94.25 vol%) with 80 μL (3-glycidioxypropyl) trimethoxysilane (GOPS) in a proportion of 0.4:100 (v/v) for enhancing adherence and mechanical stability of the coating. The solution was mixed with 1 mL of 5% (v/v) dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) for minimising the conductivity loss due to adding GOPS (Håkansson et al., 2017). The mixture which from herein we refer to as PEDOT:PSS solution was stirred for 6h at room temperature (Fig. 1A–iii), before dip coating the PU cylinders. The first dip-coating round started out by immersing the pristine PU cylinders into the PEDOT:PSS solution. PU cylinders were left overnight on an orbital shaker at 200 rpm (Fig. 1A–iii). The treated cylinders were then dried at 120 °C in a muffle furnace for 1 h, with the first 20 min inside a revolving grid for an even distribution of the PEDOT:PSS solution (Fig. 1A–iv). After the 1st dip-coating round, the PU/PEDOT:PSS cylinders were positioned facing the substrate and coinciding with the circular and planar Au electrodes, then carefully placed into the muffle in an upright position for a final annealing step, fixing the electrode to the substrate with an average contact area of $67\% \pm 13\%$ (Zeiss AxioZoom.V16, software ZEN 3.3 blue edition).

Fig. 1. Fabrication and characterization of PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes. A) Fabrication includes: (i) cleaning, (ii) hydrophilization, (iii) soaking, and (iv) annealing; B) Setup; C) Median pore diameter as a function of PEDOT:PSS layer thickness measured for each dip-coating rounds ($n = 3$), red dotted lines represent the trendline; Inset shows porosity as a function of PEDOT:PSS layer thickness ($n = 3$); D) I-V curves from 1 to 2x dip-coating rounds ($n = 3$) with the extracted conductivity; Inset shows image taken with scanning electron microscopy of a 2x dip-coated porous electrode. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

The Au electrodes consisted of a glass substrate on which circular electrodes of 50 nm Au on top of a 10 nm Ti adhesion layer were evaporated through a shadow mask (Edwards High Vacuum 4P thermal evaporator). The Au electrodes had a surface area of 10 mm² and an inter-electrode distance of 6 mm. Due to large surface area of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrode, of 240 cm², the area of the circular Au pad and strip-line was disregarded.

2.2. Fabrication of PEDOT:PSS by potentiostatic electropolymerization

Precursors were prepared by mixing 3,4-Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT) monomer (0.1 % (w/v) 0.01 M, Sigma Aldrich) with poly (sodium-4-styrene sulfonate) powder (PSSNa, 0.7 % (w/v), Sigma Aldrich) with 100 ml of distilled water in a beaker. After 3h of mixing with a magnetic stirrer, the precursors mix was left for 1h to settle down precipitates. The electropolymerization was performed on 10 mm² Au electrodes, the same area used in the PU/PEDOT:PSS contacts. After a 1-min treatment with oxygen plasma (200 W), the precursors were pipetted into a small container of a three-electrode setup consisting of a gold working electrode (WE), a platinum wire (0.5 mm diameter, Sigma Aldrich) counter electrode (CE) and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (RE), as shown in Fig. S2A. Potentiostatic deposition was conducted using three cycles of a constant potential of 0.85V for 60 s (PGSTAT 302N-Basic, Autolab). Visual inspection of PEDOT:PSS deposition on planar Au electrodes was made with SEM (section 2.8) as shown in Fig. S2B.

2.3. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS measurements were carried out with a potentiostat (PGSTAT 302N-Basic, Autolab), equipped with a MULTI4 multiplexer with 3 individual channels allowing automated sequential measurements on a batch of three replicates. For each replicate a drilled polyether ether ketone (PEEK) well was screw fixed on top of the substrate with two PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes, with similar area of 240 cm² as illustrated in Fig. 1B. This well served as a container for the electrolyte solution and/or for the cell suspension. The PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes were located inside the well and connected with a small strip-line to the contact pad outside the well. The impedance measurements were performed by connecting the contact pads outside the electrolyte solution. EIS was measured in the frequency range of 0.1 mHz–100 kHz for porous PU/PEDOT:PSS and 1 mHz to 100 kHz for planar PEDOT:PSS, with an AC voltage of 20 mV. A two-electrode system was preferred instead of a conventional three-electrode system due to long-term evaporation concerns, reference electrode misplacement against all replicates and also due to reference electrode contamination. A comparison of impedance and phase angle as a function of frequency, for both two and three-electrode setups (using a BASi Re-6 Reference Electrode) in 100 mM KCl is provided in Fig. S3 and reveals an excellent agreement between both configurations.

The equivalent circuit model was extracted using ZVIEW software. Two distinct cell densities of 1x10⁵ cell/mL and 1x10⁷ cell/mL were loaded with 3 ml of a three-week culture of *L. segnis*. The EIS measurements consisted of three replicates per each cell density used and were recorded continuously for 14 days with no nutrient refreshment. Each measuring well was kept in standard growth conditions.

2.4. Morphological and electrical characterization of PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes

The surface area of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes was determined by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis with nitrogen (Micromeritics ASAP, 2000) (n = 10). All samples were outgassed using heat and/or vacuum prior to analysis. Median pore diameter and porosity were determined by mercury porosimetry, (Micromeritics AutoPore IV 9500, Mercury Porosimeter). PEDOT:PSS layer thickness

was measured from SEM images taken on peeled PEDOT:PSS layers previously induced by soaking the PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes under 90 % ethanol under mechanical deformation as illustrated in Fig. S4. The I–V curve was determined using a two-point probe setup in a Semiconductor Device Analyzer (Keysight B1500A) as in (Cotta et al., 2024). The conductivity measurement was performed in 8 cylindrical samples (n = 4 per dip-coating cycle). The cylinder face was fixed into a copper strip with a silver ink (Silver Conductive Paint, RS Pro). The I-V curves were performed using the source/measure units (SMU) of the Keysight B1500A, with a sweep voltage from 0 to 100 mV and a 1 mV voltage step. The conductivity was determined by the multiplicative inverse value of the resistivity according to the second Ohm's law. The electrode cross-section was $S = \pi r^2$ with $r = 0.55/2$ cm and $L = 1$ cm. The conductance (σ) was achieved by linear regression (Cotta et al., 2024). No significant voltage loss along the electrode height was found.

2.5. Taxonomic identification of the strain A2O 2268

A microalgal strain identified as *Chlamydomonas* sp. A2O 2268 was purchased from the company A2O and cultured in BG11 culture medium (Sigma). The species name was determined by molecular biology tools. Cells were collected by centrifugation of 0.5 mL culture and disrupted using a mixer mill (MM200 Retsch, Germany) for 5 min. Genomic DNA was extracted using NucleoSpin Plant II (Macherey-Nagel). The PCR and sequencing service was outsourced to StabVida (stabvida.com). Primers used for obtaining sequences of the 18S rRNA gene included the universal amplification primers used for eukaryotic algae 18S-F and 18S-R and originated a sequence of 1255 bp (Katana et al., 2001). Primers used for amplification of *rbcl* were 1AB_rbcLF and 1AB_rbcLR and originated a sequence of 580 bp (Ghosh et al., 2011). Sequencing reads were assembled with SeqAssem (SequentiX) and manually edited by visual inspection of sequencing chromatograms. The sequences were loaded into GenBank blastn search engine from NCBI (blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). The combined results from the two gene sequences indicate that the organism is highly similar to *Lobochlamys segnis*, a species of microalgae previously known as *Chlamydomonas segnis* (Proschold et al., 2001).

2.6. Growth curve of *Lobochlamys segnis* and exopolysaccharides (EPS) formation

The culture was started by diluting a three week precultivated inoculum with medium to a final cell density of 4 x10⁵ cell/mL. The conventional growth curve was performed on cells growing in a multi-well plate and cell density was estimated by counting every other day with a Brand-Blaubrand Sigma-Aldrich counting chamber (n = 3). All cells were cultivated for 14 days in a growth chamber (Aralab FITO-CLIMA 600 PDH) with temperature of 18 °C, photoperiod of 12h:12h and a light intensity of 30 μmol/m²/s provided by cool white daylight fluorescent lamps.

Growth of *Lobochlamys segnis* was modelled with MATLAB R2024, using a logistic function, which describes the relation between numeric growth (cell density) of a microorganism as a function of time applied to model bacterial population growth (Vandamme et al., 2021a), (Vandamme et al., 2021b), (Verhulst, 1847), (Verhulst, 1845), and to microalgal growth (Kiss and Németh, 2019), (Xin et al., 2010), (Amaral et al., 2024). The logistic function is described by Eq. (1):

$$f(x) = \frac{x(t_0) + x(t_{max})}{1 + e^{(a-k*(t-t_{mid}))}} \quad (1)$$

where x is cell density at a given time (cells/mL); t is the time (days), t_0 is the first time-point after 24 h, t_{mid} is the value of the logistic function midpoint (day); k is the logistic growth rate of the curve (day⁻¹). The numerator of Eq. (1) is the carrying capacity viz., the maximum cell density achieved during growth, a is the logistic model constant indicating the relative position to the origin.

The exopolysaccharides (EPS) production of cells was also investigated during growth curves. The culture was started by diluting a three week precultivated inoculum with medium to a final cell density of 4×10^5 cell/mL. A volume of 2 mL was distributed over different glass test tubes and the EPS production was recorded by sampling and imaging the cells every other day. Microscopic slides were prepared by adding 3 μ L (drawing ink, Pelikan) to 25 μ L of cells collected from the bottom of the test tube according to the negative staining methods used for mucilaginous microalgae (Leya, 2022). The ink coloured the surrounding medium and highlighted the EPS. Micrographs were obtained with a Zeiss axiocam 305 color microcamera coupled to an Axio Zoom microscope (Zeiss Axio Zoom V16, software ZEN 3.3 blue edition). The occupied area by cells and by EPS were measured over 14 days in an interval of 2 days by counting 100 cells/day through the software Fiji 1.54f.

2.7. Determination of the percentage occupied by cells and bound EPS (bEPS) in PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes

The volume of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes was determined by pipetting and measuring the maximum volume of medium held in the PU/PEDOT:PSS electrode pores. After the oxygen plasma treatment, the electrodes ($n = 3$) were positioned upright and culture medium was added at the top until the maximum volume retained in the electrodes was identified (before it started to accumulate at the base), which was determined to be, $V_{electrode} = 130 \pm 1.858 \mu\text{L}$. The cell number adherent to the electrode ($cells_{electrode}$) was then calculated by multiplying the cell concentration ($cell_{concentration}$) estimated by counting in cells/mL with $V_{electrode}$, in each day, as:

$$cells_{electrode} = cell_{concentration} \times V_{electrode} \quad (2)$$

Then, to determine the total area occupied by cells in the electrode (A_{total}), the area of a single cell plus the area occupied by bound excreted bEPS for each cell ($Area_{cell + bEPS}$) was multiplied by the number of cells existing in the electrodes ($cells_{electrode}$) for each day as:

$$A_{total} = Area_{cell + bEPS} \times cells_{electrode} \quad (3)$$

Since the surface area of the electrode ($A_{electrode,s}$) was previously determined to be 240 cm^2 (with BET analysis), the percentage of occupation in the electrode surface (A%) is given by:

$$A\% = \frac{A_{total} \times 100}{A_{electrode,s}} \quad (4)$$

2.8. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes were analyzed using SEM for the morphology determination and at the end of the experiments, for observation of adherent cells. The samples were prepared for SEM analysis by depositing a 10 nm thick gold/palladium metallization layer, in a plasma generator Quorum SC7620 Mini Sputter Coater with a Glow Discharge System with an Au/Pd sputter target. The microstructural analysis of the surfaces was performed using a TESCAN VEGA 3 SBH Easy Probe SEM with a tungsten-heated cathode. The images were acquired with a working voltage of 5 kV and using the secondary electron detector.

2.9. Statistical analysis

Variance analysis was performed by employing a two-tailed Student's *t*-test with MatLab2024.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemically stable PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes for cell monitoring

Polyurethane (PU) cylinders were first cleaned and hydrophilized with oxygen plasma (Fig. 1A–i and ii), followed by a dip-coated process with PEDOT:PSS (Fig. 1A–iii). The PU/PEDOT:PSS cylinders were then annealed as detailed in methods (Fig. 1A–iv). Two dip-coating rounds were performed to ensure PEDOT:PSS was evenly distributed through the porous structure. The median pore diameter decreased from 218 μm (pristine) to 163 μm (2x) over the two consecutive dip-coating rounds (Fig. 1C). The porosity remained stable up to two dip-coating rounds, with values varying from 58.58% (pristine) to 56.30% (2x), indicating only a 2% variation, as shown by mercury porosimetry analysis in inset of Fig. 1C. The electrical conductivity is extracted from two-point probe I-V measurements as a function of dip-coating rounds. The measured I-V traces and calculated conductivity are presented in (Fig. 1D) with $n = 3$. The first dip-coating round (1x) increases the sample conductivity to $5.87 \pm 0.59 \text{ S/m}$. The second dip-coating round increases the conductivity to $15.86 \pm 1.79 \text{ S/m}$ (2x) while maintaining the internal electrode structure relatively intact (as shown by SEM image of a 2x coated PU/PEDOT:PSS electrode in inset of Fig. 1D). There seems to exist a proportionality between the standard deviation and the applied voltage, particularly for two-dip coating rounds, which could relate to the complicated RC network caused by the PEDOT:PSS distribution in the pores. Porosity is maintained with a variation of less than 3% and pore diameter is slightly decreasing as a function of dip-coating rounds as a consequence of increasing PEDOT:PSS layer thickness.

An electrical double layer emerges at any electrode/electrolyte interface. The corresponding Helmholtz double layer capacitance depends on the applied potential, ionic strength of the solution and, most importantly, on the electrode surface area. Hence, in order to inspect the homogeneity of PEDOT:PSS coatings on the porous PU substrates (and absence of pore-clogging which would reduce the electrode surface area) we performed EIS using 100 mM KCl solution to evaluate the change in capacitance and impedance of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes with dip-coating rounds. The impedance of the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes decreases as a function PEDOT:PSS layer thickness (Fig. S5A), particularly at low frequencies, indicating that PEDOT:PSS adhered to the porous microstructure. The decrease in impedance is mostly due to the increase in capacitance. The measured low frequency capacitance increases $\sim 14.3 \mu\text{F/cm}^2$ (Fig. S5B) per dip-coating cycle. The phase angle, at low frequencies discloses a capacitive behavior for both dip-coating cycles, with a phase angle near 90° (inset of Fig. S5A). The increase in capacitance agrees with the accumulation of PEDOT:PSS which increases the electrode surface area, decreases the electrode impedance and suggests a continuous spread of PEDOT:PSS across the pore walls which corroborates with SEM imaging (inset of Fig. 1D) and mercury porosimetry analysis shown in Fig. 1C. The maximum in the dielectric loss spectrum represented in the inset of Fig. 1E is given by the equivalent parallel conductance over the angular frequency.

3.1.1. Long-term stability assay with BG11 culture medium-only

Before adding cells to the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes, a long-term stability assay was performed by continuous monitoring EIS over 14 days, on 3 independent wells with BG11 culture medium-only. Fig. 2A shows the small-signal impedance as a function of the frequency between 0.1 mHz and 100 kHz, with only BG11 culture medium, with three replicates, which we consider our baseline. During the 14 days no significant impedance variations were measured, indicating an excellent electrochemical stability of the porous electrodes. The inset of Fig. 2A provides a representation of the double RC equivalent circuit. At low bias, the current depends linearly on voltage. This resistance comprises various contributions, including from cells, EPS, PEDOT:PSS and contact resistance between Au and PEDOT:PSS, and is herein represented as

Fig. 2. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy of PU/PEDOT: PSS porous electrodes in BG11 medium for 14 days (n=3). A) Impedance as a function of frequency between 0.1 mHz and 100 kHz. The inset shows the equivalent circuit of an electrode-electrolyte interface, consisting of an ideal capacitor (C_p) representing the capacitance in parallel with a charge transfer resistance (R_{el}) connected in series to the solution resistance (R_{sol}). The parallel capacitive effect, denoted as (C_{sol}), is typically negligible; B) Extracted Phase (θ) as a function of frequency between 0.1 mHz and 100 kHz, measured (circles) and fitted (solid line) (n = 3). The inset shows the extracted equivalent parallel capacitance, C_p and Loss (G_p/ω), arrow indicates the Maxwell-Wagner relaxation frequency (f_r).

electrode resistance, R_{el} . The equivalent circuit then comprises a resistance (R_{el}) in parallel with a capacitor (C_p) which are connected in series to the solution resistance (R_{sol}). Additionally, there is a parallel capacitive effect, denoted as C_{sol} which is negligible. Since both electrodes are practically equal, only one electrode interface has been accounted. Fig. 2B illustrates the extracted phase. At low frequencies, the phase angle continues to reveal an almost ideal capacitive behavior. Inset of Fig. 2B shows the extracted equivalent parallel capacitance, C_p (blue) intercepted by the loss curve (red). The black arrow corresponds to the Maxwell-Wagner relaxation frequency, $f_r = 0.01$ Hz, which indicates the dispersion in capacitance obtained from the maximum in the corresponding dielectric loss spectrum.

The impedance can be calculated by Eq. (5):

$$Z(\omega) = R_{sol} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_p + \frac{1}{R_{el}}} \quad (5)$$

The solution resistance, R_{sol} , is represented by the spreading of current from the measuring electrode to a distant counter electrode, within the electrolyte media, and can be estimated as:

$$R_{sol} = \frac{\rho}{4r} \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the specific resistivity of the solution and r is the radius of a linear cylinder face. The real and imaginary parts of the impedance, Z' and Z'' are given by Eqs (7) and (8) respectively:

$$Z' = R_{sol} + \left(\frac{R_{el}}{1 + (\omega R_{el} C_p)^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$Z'' = \left(\frac{\omega R_{el}^2 C_p}{1 + (\omega R_{el} C_p)^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

The maximum loss is obtained at the Maxwell-Wagner frequency, f_r , that is given by (Hirschorn et al., 2010)

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi R_{sol} C_p} \quad (9)$$

The extracted values for the resistance R_{el} , capacitance C_p , and spreading resistance R_{sol} are presented in Table S1. Table S1 shows that by using Eq. (6), a specific resistivity, ρ , for the BG11 medium is

calculated to be $291.48 \pm 20.10 \Omega \text{ cm}$ in fair agreement with others (Patel et al., 2017).

3.2. Detection sensitivity scales with cell density

After performing a long-term stability assay with BG11 medium we seeded the cells in the PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes. We note the simplicity of initiating the electrical monitoring process as well as effortless EIS data extraction which was done automatically in the commercially available potentiostat. Cellular adhesion and changes in cell density have been monitored continuously using EIS over 14 days. We monitored several frequencies across the entire measured spectrum to identify those that best capture the growth of *L. segnis* cells on the electrode. We noted that the impedance at lower frequencies displayed a higher change, particularly at 0.1 mHz. Hence, we selected the frequency of 0.1 mHz for analysing cell adhesion and growth. High frequency events, above f_r , at 100 Hz were also analyzed over time (Fig. 3).

Our initial EIS experiments were performed with a cell density of 10^5 cells/mL, which corresponded to $\sim 0.5\%$ of electrode coverage and the maximum of 74.53%, achieved at day 10 (Table S3), in agreement with the image taken by SEM (Fig. 3A) and to the minimum starting cell seeding densities employed in most biotechnological contexts (Bohutskyi et al., 2016). Cell adhesion didn't significantly alter the impedance at day 0, given that the impedance with medium-only was $37050 \pm 3028 \Omega$ and the impedance recorded with cells at day 0 was $37105 \pm 3270 \Omega$. Yet, over the whole 14 days of growth, the low frequency impedance increased over 3 k Ω , to $40024 \pm 3610 \Omega$ (Fig. 3B). At 100 Hz the impedance with media-only did not vary distinguishably over time, with an averaged value of $270 \pm 4 \Omega$ considering all 14 days. With the 10^5 cell/mL culture, it slightly evolved from 321 Ω to 339 Ω at day 2, followed by a relatively stable impedance with an average $341 \pm 4 \Omega$ until day 14 (Fig. 3C). The impedance changes are mostly due to the capacitance variation. The increase in cell number and EPS production yield thicker films adherent to the porous electrodes, which lower the capacitance and increases the measured impedance. Indeed, at low frequency, the trend in capacitance decreases from day 0, with 45 ± 2 mF to day 8, with 42 ± 1 mF, followed by a stable capacitance of 42 ± 2 mF until day 14 (Fig. 3D). At high frequencies the capacitance barely changed over 14 days ($5.2 \times 10^{-8} \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-8}$ F) (Fig. 3E).

In order to inspect the effect of cell coverage on the sensitivity of the monitoring system, we increased cell density to 10^7 cells/mL which

Fig. 3. Adhesion and growth of *Lobochlamys segnis* cells on PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes. A) Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) observation of *L. segnis* cells adherent to the porous electrodes at the 14th day of the experiment. Zoom in represented by yellow dashed line; B) Modulus of impedance as a function of time with distinct cell concentrations at 0.1 MHz and C) at 100 Hz in BG11 medium (black diamonds), 10⁵ cells/mL (blue squares) and 10⁷ cells/mL (red squares) with $n = 3$; D) Evolution of capacitance recorded at 0.1 MHz and E) at 100 Hz as a function of time where 10⁷ cells/mL are represented as red triangles, with $n = 3$; F) Capacitance as a function of impedance recorded for 10⁵ (top blue squares) and 10⁷ cells/mL (bottom red squares); G) $|Z|$ at 0.1 MHz, measured in the porous electrodes with adherent cells ($n = 3$) and growth curve obtained with cell density 10⁵ cell/mL ($n = 3$), both normalized to percentage (min = 0, max = 100), as a function of time (the same trend and k were determined for 10⁷ cell/mL, Fig. S6). The dashed lines represent the logistical fit, the growth rate of cells, k , was determined for cell concentration over time $k_{cells} = 0.85 \pm 0.05$ and for EIS progression over time, $k_z = 0.75 \pm 0.06$; H) The relative change in impedance as a function of time. Inset represents the relative change in cell density. Black arrow indicates the exponential phase. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

corresponded to an initial cell coverage of 5.5% at day 0, and a peak cell coverage of 74.5% at day 10. Increasing the cell density to 10⁷ cells/mL resulted in a change of low frequency impedance of 11.5 kΩ comparing to the lower density culture, due to higher cell adhesion from 37100 ± 3270 Ω to 48580 ± 3390 Ω, respectively, at day 0 ($p < 0.05$). Following this substantial impedance change due to higher cell adhesion, the evolution of impedance was monitored over 14 days. At 0.1 MHz, we recorded a change of 3.42 kΩ, from 48580 ± 3390 Ω at day 0 to 52000 ± 1970 Ω at day 14. At high frequencies, at 100 Hz, the impedance slightly increased, from 361 ± 35.90 Ω at day 0, to 415 ± 51 Ω at day 14 (Fig. 3B and C).

The behaviour in capacitance is similar to that of described with the initial cell seeding of 10⁵ cells/mL (Fig. 3D and E). Table S2 contains the values in detail. The increase in low-frequency impedance over time is mostly due to the decrease in the capacitance, as ascertained by the linear relation between capacitance and impedance, for both cell densities, depicted in (Fig. 3F).

The *L. segnis* logistic growth curve on the PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes is in close agreement with conventional cell-counting

performed in parallel to the impedance recordings and with literature where the growth rate has been reported as 0.63 cells/day (Puzanskiy et al., 2018). From our cell counting, *L. segnis* growth started with an exponential phase from day 2 until day 8, followed by a linear growth where we extracted a logistic growth rate of $k_{cells} = 0.85$ cells/day (Fig. 3G). Then, at day 10, cell density started declining. We report a slightly higher growth rate, which may stem from using a different strain, which may naturally display higher growth rate. It may also be caused by the use of growth promoting N-rich medium BG11, which stimulates microalgal growth, contrary to the decelerating cultivation conditions reported elsewhere (Puzanskiy et al., 2018). The impedance over time at 0.1 MHz followed a similar trend to the conventional growth curve, with an impedance increase at the beginning of the growth curve coinciding to the exponential and linear phase of growth, followed by an electrochemically stable stationary stage. We applied the logistic model to the measured low-frequency impedance over time and retrieved the logistic growth of $k_z = 0.75$, in close agreement with the estimated $k_{cells} = 0.85$ cells/day. The normalized impedance and standard deviations as a function of time are in good accordance with the

numeric growth and standard deviations ascertained by cell counting with conventional methods. To highlight the exponential phase, the relative impedance change was analyzed as ΔZ according to Eq. (10):

$$\Delta Z = \frac{Z_{n+1} - Z_n}{Z_n} \quad (10)$$

The cell density over time was analyzed using the same methodology as in Eq. (10). In both cases, the exponential phase, at the 4th day interval exhibits the larger relative growth as highlighted in (Fig. 3H) and respective inset with change in cell density. We further noted that the relative change in low frequency impedance ΔZ could be a valuable prediction approach for exponential growth given its ability to early detect the exponential phase, even before conventional cell counting methods as shown in Fig. 3H. The early increase in impedance could be linked with EPS yields which will be discussed in the next section.

Cells adhered well to the PEDOT:PSS surfaces and remained viable with no observable morphological alterations during the full 14 days (Fig. S7). To ascertain the advantage of the 3D porous electrodes regarding conventional planar electrodes, a direct comparison of the low frequency impedance, of planar and 3D PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes, was performed using the same cell density of 10^7 cells/mL. Details on device fabrication by potentiostatic deposition and impedance benchmarking are provided in Fig. S2. To ascertain the success of the electropolymerization, the electrochemical impedance and phase angle of both planar and 3D porous PEDOT:PSS electrodes were recorded and compared in Fig. S2C. Expectedly, the measured impedance is strongly dependent on the electrode area. PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes with an area of 240 cm^2 exhibit a decrease by nearly 2 orders of magnitude when compared to planar PEDOT:PSS electrodes of 10 mm^2 .

The low frequency impedance over time, for planar and 3D porous electrodes is shown in Fig. S8 A, after cell seeding. Similar to the 3D porous electrodes, the high frequency impedance and capacitance were not found to be a good proxy for cellular adhesion and proliferation. On the other hand, for both planar and 3D electrodes, the low frequency

impedance effectively translates cellular adhesion and increases over time, up to 4–6 days (Fig. S8 A). Interestingly, and in contrast to the smaller planar area, the larger surface area of porous PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes allowed the monitorization of the full growth curve, particularly in detecting the exponential phase (Fig. S8C), which is essential to determine the logistical parameter of growth, k (Fig. S8F).

3.3. Exopolysaccharides (EPS) formation and their contribution to EIS

The initial part of the normalized impedance curve (between day 0 and day 6) seen in Fig. 3G is higher than the conventional growth curve. We hypothesize that high production of exopolysaccharides (EPS) by each cell may be the major contributing excretion to the higher impedance at the beginning of growth, since a dominating presence of EPS was detected by negative staining (Fig. 4A). The cells produce and excrete EPS which is bound to the cell surface at the beginning and then part of it detaches and dissolves to the surrounding medium at later stages of growth, also seen in other studies (Leya, 2022). We therefore followed EPS formation in *L. segnis* cells and found that the highest production occurs on day 8 (Fig. 4A), when impedance at 0.1 mHz reaches the highest plateau (Fig. 3B). The average size of the cells per day remained stable over time (Fig. 4B) although exhibiting a marginal variability in all growth stages. Bafana et al. showed that optimum EPS production in *Chlamydomonas* may reach as much as 628 mg/L (Bafana, 2013) while excreted molecules and metabolites such as proteins, phenols, vitamins, allelopathic chemicals, hormones, lipids (Liu et al., 2016) are released in much lower concentrations. Protein concentrations of $30 \text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ maximum were found in the culture medium after cultivation of microalgae, and these concentrations drop to $2 \text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ if the cells are bound with a mucilaginous sheath (Zych et al., 2022). It is therefore very likely that the observed changes in impedance are mostly due to EPS rather than from excreted metabolites and/or molecules.

Cells and EPS both occupy the PU/PEDOT:PSS surface area and must be collaboratively contributing to the impedance change. Hence

Fig. 4. Exopolysaccharides (EPS) formation over time in *Lobo-chlamys segnis*. A) Observation of EPS around the cells over time, from day 0 to day 12, evidenced by contrast staining with drawing ink (scale bar 20 μm); B) *L. segnis* cell area distribution (μm^2) for 12 days ($n = 700$). Red line represents the Gaussian Fit with full width at half maximum (FWHM) of $50.54 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$; C) EPS and single cell area (μm^2), represented in logarithmic scale, determined by image analysis every other day. Black circles refer to total area average occupied by a single cell ($n = 100$), purple diamonds refer to area occupied only by EPS; D) Normalized occupied area by EPS (purple diamonds) ($n = 100$) and low frequency $|Z|$ ($n = 3$) as a function of days; E) R_{sol} as a function of time for 10^7 (red triangles) and 10^5 (black diamonds) cells/mL. The dashed lines represent the corresponding linear fit curves and rate of change. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

(Fig. 4C), shows the estimated occupied area (μm^2) by single cells (black circles) and EPS (pink diamonds) over time. The estimation allows a direct correlation between the measured impedance at 0.1 mHz and the EPS production given in (Fig. 4D). Indeed, by accounting for the EPS production over time, the growth estimation is improved, particularly for the growth period (0–6 days). We may therefore assume that the impedance recorded on the PU/PEDOT:PSS electrodes must account for EPS formation.

The maximum excretion of EPS occurring at the beginning of the decline stage of growth can be detected with EIS. The excretion dynamics of EPS to the extracellular media are very likely influencing the solution resistivity, and therefore should be proportional to the equivalent circuit parameter R_{sol} and should be highly influenced by distinct cell densities. Hence (Fig. 4E), shows the R_{sol} parameter as a function of cell density and time. From 10^5 cells/mL to 10^7 cells/mL, the solution resistance rate changed from $0.70 \Omega \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ to $7.61 \Omega \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$. Additionally, on day 12, the solution resistance exhibited a relatively significant increase, from 398 to 407 Ω , coinciding with the maximum EPS dilution to the extracellular medium. The maximum dilution of EPS to the medium can be inferred by the total area of EPS observed in the micrographs over time. In detail, the EPS diluted to the medium was ascertained by staining with drawing ink, performed from day 0 to day 12 and recorded in micrographs, as shown in Fig. 4A.

The area occupied by adherent cells and EPS on the porous electrode as a function of time is shown in Table S3. Based on the biological growth over time, we estimate that $\sim 0.5\%$ of the electrode was covered by adherent cells and EPS on day 10, when the initial cell concentration of 10^5 cells/mL was used (0.012% initial coverage at day 0) (Table S3). This low cell density generated a low frequency impedance curve over time, comparable to the biological growth curve, as shown in Fig. 3G, which evidences the high sensitivity of the method to estimate growth, even at low cell concentrations. The system sensitivity and influence of initial cell concentration on the ability of EIS to serve as a proxy for cell growth was determined by setting up an experiment with an initial cell concentration of 10^7 cells/mL leading to a percentage of occupied area of $\sim 75\%$ at day 10 and a much clearer trend in relation to control experiments with medium-only.

The bound portion of the EPS in *L. segnis* (bEPS) is constituted by capsular polysaccharides with a highly branched random coil structure made of galactose, glucuronic acid and glucose sugars, contrary to the more common hyaluronan-based linear polysaccharides (Schiano di Visconte et al., 2021). EPS are produced by many mucilaginous species to protect the cell from the surrounding osmotic pressure. Rheological properties of *L. segnis* bEPS include a higher thickening property, comparing with other microalgal EPS (Schiano di Visconte et al., 2021). The presence of a thick and insulating layer adjacent to the cell wall contributes to the total area occupied by cells on the electrode and to the evolving impedance at low frequency proportional to cell growth. For applications in large bioreactors, this should be considered when used for continuous EIS growth monitoring of mucilaginous species which retain bEPS prior to EPS release to the culture medium. In addition, we envisage further detection optimization by finetuning the mechanical and surface properties of the large porous electrodes to the biological cell of interest.

4. Conclusions

This study presents the applicability of EIS to monitor real-time growth of *L. segnis* and their bound EPS adherent to large-surface area PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrode. Both cells and concomitant EPS yields adhere to the PU/PEDOT:PSS surface and collaboratively contributed to the exponential growth of the low frequency impedance at 0.1 mHz, from day 2 until day 8, followed by a linear growth where we extracted a logistic growth rate of $k = 0.75$ cells/day, in close agreement to the biological growth rate reported by others using standard cell counting methods. The change in impedance is owed to the varying capacitance.

As cells grow through the large porous surface, they produce EPS and concomitant thicker adherent films which diminishes the capacitance and increases the impedance.

The EIS sensitivity scales with cells density, from 10^5 to 10^7 cells/ml, and even with a minimum electrode coverage of $\sim 0.5\%$, the low frequency impedance was still able to mimic the biological growth curve, with EPS production significantly influencing impedance recordings during the initial 0–6 days. Furthermore, the solution resistance rate, extracted via the circuit parameter R_{sol} was sensitive to the maximum EPS solubilization time-point, and showed a direct correlation with distinct seeding densities.

The combination of EIS and large PU/PEDOT:PSS porous electrodes enables real-time high-resolution monitoring of growth dynamics and EPS production and release to the medium, even in low-concentration cultures, highlighting its potential for biomass growth monitoring and real-time detection of EPS production inside bioreactor tanks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Francisco C. Cotta: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Raquel Amaral:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Felipe L. Bacellar:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Diogo Correia:** Data curation, Methodology. **Kamal Asadi:** Writing – review & editing. **Paulo R.F. Rocha:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2025.117260>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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